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Spider wasps (Hymenoptera, Pompilidae) from the Southeastern Iran, Kerman

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ABSTRACT. The spider wasps (Hymenoptera: Pompilidae) of Kerman province were faunistically investigated. A total of 17 species of 12 genera belonging to three subfamilies, Ceropalinae, pepsinae and pompilinae were collected during 2017–2018 and identified. Among the collected material, three species of Ceropalinae, *Ceropales juncoi* Giner, 1945, *Ceropales kriebchaumeri* Magretti, 1884, *Ceropales maroccana* de Beaumont, 1947 and a single species of Pompilinae, *Agenioideus gentilis* (Klug, 1834) are recorded for the first time for the fauna of Iran. Geographical distribution of each species in Kerman province, Iran and outside Iran are presented.

Key words: Hymenoptera, Spider wasps, Fauna, New records, Iran

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Introduction

The family Pompilidae known as 'spider wasps' are the largest family among aculeate wasps that contains about 5,000 species belonging to 130 genera, worldwide (Aguilar et al., 2013). Members of this family are found in a wide range of habitats, especially in tropical regions (Wasbauer, 1995). The pompilids are long-legged solitary wasps that can be distinguished from all other wasps by the presence of oblique mesopleural suture (Pitts et al., 2006). Adult wasps feed on flower nectar, but they hunt spiders to feed their larvae, that is why they are called spider wasps (Grimaldi & Engel, 2004). Based on Waichert et al. (2015), the Pompilidae comprises five subfamilies, Ceropalinae, Ctenocerinae, Notocyphinae, Pepsinae and Pompilinae, of which the last two subfamilies have highest species abundance. Some recent faunistic and taxonomic studies have been carried out on Iranian Pompilidae (Wahis, 2000; Wahis & Schmid-Egger, 2002; Ebrahimi, 2006; Ebrahimi et al., 2008; Amiresmaili et al., 2010a, 2010b, 2011; Amiresmaili & Barari, 2012; Falahatpishe et al., 2016; Schmid-Egger et al., 2018) but still little is known on their taxonomy and distribution. The last updated list of Iranian Pompilidae (Enayatnia et al., 2018) included 162 species belonging to 41 genera and three subfamilies. The aim of this paper is to study the pompilid fauna of Kerman province and complete with new information on the distributional data.

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Material and methods

This research was carried out during 2017 and 2018. Specimens were collected from different habitats of Kerman province (Southeastern Iran) (Fig. 1) using sweep net and Malaise traps. The collected specimens were preserved in ethanol 75%, later prepared using the AXA method (van Achterberg, 2009), mounted or pinned and examined under Nikon[®] SMZ800 stereomicroscope. Many genera of the Palaearctic Pompilidae are not revised or available keys and revisions are incomplete for Iranian fauna. For this reason, species were mainly identified with unpublished keys of Christian Schmid-Egger or by comparisons with identified species deposited in his private collection. Primary revisions of the new recorded species for Iran are presented in Wolf (1985, 1986, 1990) and Móczár (1968, 1986, 1989). For full references of Iranian Pompilidae see references section in Enayatnia et al. (2018), from which the distributional records of the species are also extracted. Specimens are deposited in the Insect Collection of the Zoological Museum of Shahid Bahonar University of Kerman, Kerman, Iran (ZMSBUK).

Figure 1. Geographic map of Kerman province.

Results

A total of 17 species belonging to 12 genera and three subfamilies, Ceropalinae, pepsinae and pompilinae were collected and identified in the present study. The subfamilies, genera and species are listed in alphabetic order. The identified material are given below. New records for Iran and for Kerman province are marked with single (*) and double (**) asterisks, respectively.

Family POMPILIDAE

Subfamily Ceropalinae Ashmead, 1900

Ceropales cribrata Costa, 1881**

Material examined: Iran, Kerman province: 1♀, Kerman County, Chatrood-Booj, 30°22'43.09" N, 56°41'55.09" E, 2365 m, 01.vi.2018-28.vi.2018, Malaise trap, (Sh. Mohebban leg.); 1♀, Koochpayeh, 30°28'50.65" N, 57°19'17.98" E, 1803 m, 28.vi.2018-19.vii.2018, Malaise trap, (Sh. Mohebban leg.).

Distribution in Iran: Fars, West Azarbaijan, Kerman (present study).

Distribution outside Iran: Europe and East Palaearctic (Wahis, 2015), Turkey (Özbek et al., 1999; Yildirim & Wahis, 2011a, 2011b).

Ceropales juncoi Giner, 1945* (Fig. 2A)

Material examined: Iran, Kerman province: 1♂, Baft County, Khabr village, 28°49'46.25" N, 56°15'40.80" E, 1448 m, 09.vii.2018-10.viii.2018, Malaise trap, (Sh. Mohebban leg.); 1♂, Khabr village, 28°49'46.25" N, 56°15'40.80" E, 1448 m, 10.viii.2018-07.ix.2018, Malaise trap (Sh. Mohebban leg.).

Distribution in Iran: Kerman province (new record from Iran).

Distribution outside Iran: Chad, Egypt, Israel, Pakistan, Somalia, Sudan, Western Sahara (van Noort, 2019).

Ceropales kriebbaumeri Magretti, 1884* (Fig. 2B)

Material examined: Iran, Kerman province: 1♂, Kerman County, Chatrood, Booj, 30°22'43.09" N, 56°41'55.09" E, 2365 m, 28.vi.2018-03.viii.2018, Malaise trap (Sh. Mohebban leg.).

Distribution in Iran: Kerman province (new record from Iran).

Distribution outside Iran: Burkina Faso, Nigeria, South Africa, Zimbabwe, Uganda (Gess & Roosenchoon, 2016).

Ceropales maculata (Fabricius, 1775)**

Material examined: Iran, Kerman province: 1♂, Kerman County, Koochpayeh, 30°28'50.65" N, 57°19'17.98" E, 1803 m, 19.vii.2018-24.viii.2018, Malaise trap (Sh. Mohebban leg.).

Distribution in Iran: Fars, Mazandaran, Tehran, Kerman (present study).

Distribution outside Iran: Europe, East Palaearctic, Near East, North Africa (Wahis, 2015), China, Korea, Mongolia (Yasumatsu, 1946), Japan (Yasumatsu & Ishikawa, 1955), Turkmenistan (Wolf, 1995), Kazakhstan (Wolf, 2004), Kyrgyzstan (Wahis, 1996; Wolf, 2004), Tadjikistan (Wolf, 2004), Mongolia (Wolf, 2005a), Turkey (Özbek et al., 1999; Yildirim & Wahis, 2011a, 2011b).

Ceropales maroccana* de Beaumont, 1947 (Fig. 2C)

Material examined: Iran, Kerman province: 1♂, Bardsir County, Dashtkar, 29°52'04.96" N, 56°38'53.36" E, 2088 m, 20.vii.2018–17.viii.2018, Malaise trap (Sh. Mohebban leg.); 1♂, Kerman County, Chatrood-Booj, 30°22'43.09" N, 56°41'55.09" E, 2365 m, 01.vi.2018–28.vi.2018, Malaise trap (Sh. Mohebban leg.).

Distribution in Iran: Kerman province (new record from Iran).

Distribution outside Iran: Southeastern Anatolia (Yildirim & Wahis, 2010).

Subfamily Pepsinae Lepeletier, 1845***Auplopus carbonarius* (Scopoli, 1763)****

Material examined: Iran, Kerman province: 1♀, Bam County, Bam, 29°06'01.7" N, 58°19'44.0" E, 1111 m, 13.v.2017–31.v.2017, Malaise trap (M. Purrezaali leg.).

Distribution in Iran: Alborz, East Azerbaijan, Fars, Golestan, Mazandaran, Kerman (present study).

Distribution outside Iran: Europe (Wahis, 2015), Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan (Wolf, 1998a), Jordan (Wolf, 1998b), Syria (Wolf, 2005b); Algeria, Britain, Israel, Japan, Lebanon, Mongolia, Morocco, Sweden (Wolf, 1971), Croatia (Wahis, 1963), France (Wahis, 1979), Greece (Priesner, 1965), Turkey (Özbek et al., 1999; Yildirim & Wahis, 2011a, 2011b); Kazakhstan (Wolf, 2003, 2005a); Tadjikistan (Wolf, 2004), Russia, Western Europe, Ukraine, Kazakhstan, Near East, Korea, Japan, North Africa (Lelej & Loktionov, 2012; Baghirov, 2014).

Auplopus nigroaurantiacus* Magretti, 1884*

Material examined: Iran, Kerman province: 1♀, Anbar Abad County, Bardeh, 28°28'04.1" N, 58°12'39.3" E, 1510 m, 23.v.2017–04.vi.2017, Malaise trap (S.M. Madjzadeh leg.); 1♀, Orzuoieye, 28°24'37.00" N, 56°27'14.27" E, 1063 m, 10.viii.2018, Swept on *Medicago sativa* (Sh. Mohebban leg.).

Distribution in Iran: Fars, Kerman (present study).

Distribution outside Iran: Natal, Zimbabwe, Senegal, Gambia, Saudi Arabia (Gadallah & El-Barty, 2011).

Subfamily Pompilinae Ashmead, 1900***Agenioideus gentilis* (Klug, 1834)*** (Fig. 2D)

Material examined: Iran, Kerman province: 1♂, Kerman County, Mahan, 30°03'22.83" N, 57°17'50.88" E, 1890 m, 04.v.2018–06.vi.2018, Malaise trap (Sh. Mohebban leg.).

Distribution in Iran: Kerman province (new record from Iran).

Distribution outside Iran: South Europe, Egypt, Israel, newly recorded from Saudi Arabia (Gadallah & El-Barty, 2011).

Agenioideus nubecula* (Costa, 1874)*

Material examined: Iran, Kerman province: 1♂, Jiroft County, Dalfard-Bondar, 29°00'36" N, 57°36'39.1" E, 2232 m, 17.vii.2017–30.viii.2017, Malaise trap (S.M. Madjzadeh leg.); 1♂, Chatrood, 30°36'24.52" N, 56°55'12.46" E, 1893 m, 06.ix.2018–12.x.2018, Malaise trap (Sh. Mohebban leg.).

Distribution in Iran: Mazandaran, Sistan-o Baluchestan, South Khorasan, Kerman (present study).

Distribution outside Iran: Eastern Anatolia, Southeastern Anatolia, Central Anatolia, Mediterranean, Aegean, Marmara (Yildirim & Wahis, 2010).

Agenioideus waltlii* (Spinola, 1838)*

Material examined: Iran, Kerman province: 1♂, Manujan County, Chermil, 27°33'13.6" N, 57°35'52" E, 445 m, 5.v.2017-22.v.2017, Malaise trap (M. Purrezaali leg.).

Distribution in Iran: Fars, Kerman (present study).

Distribution outside Iran: Egypt, Israel, North Africa, Saudi Arabia (Gadallah & El-Barty, 2011).

Agenioideus zarudnyi* (Gussakovskij, 1932)*

Material examined: Iran, Kerman province: 1♀, Jiroft County, Jiroft, 28°36'13.7"N, 57°49'42.0" E, 652 m, 04.vi.2017-09.vi.2017, Malaise trap (S.M. Madjzadeh leg.).

Distribution in Iran: Sistan-o Baluchestan, South Khorasan, Kerman (present study).

Distribution outside Iran: Algeria (Wolf, 1988, 1990). This species is recorded for the first time from Asia.

Figure 2. The newly recorded pompilid species, habitus, lateral view: **A.** *Ceropales juncoi* Giner, 1945, male, **B.** *Ceropales kriechbaumeri* Magretti, 1884, male, **C.** *Ceropales maroccana* de Beaumont, 1947, male, **D.** *Agenioideus gentilis* (Klug, 1834), male.

Arachnotheutes aegyptorum* (Priesner, 1955)*

Material examined: Iran, Kerman province: 1♂, Kerman County, Chatrood, 30°36'24.52" N, 56°55'12.46" E, 1893 m, 03.viii.2018–06.xi.2018, Malaise trap (Sh. Mohebban leg.); 1♂, Anbar Abad, Bardeh, 28°28'04.1" N, 58°12'39.3" E, 1510 m, 13.iv.2017–05.v.2017, Malaise trap, (S.M. Madjdzadeh leg.).

Distribution in Iran: Fars, Kerman (present study).

Distribution outside Iran: Egypt, Israel, Libya, Somalia, UAE ([Schmid-Egger, 2017](#)).

Ferreola barrei* (Radoszkowski, 1893)*

Material examined: Iran, Kerman province: 1♂, Anbar Abad County, Roodfarq, 28°29'4" N, 58°9' 56.2" E, 1429 m, 21.iv.2017–05.v.2017, Malaise trap (M. Purrezaali leg.).

Distribution in Iran: Fars, Alborz, Kerman (present study).

Distribution outside Iran: Turkmenistan, Afghanistan ([Schmid-Egger et al., 2018](#)).

Icazus arcanus* (Priesner, 1955)*

Material examined: Iran, Kerman province: 1♀, Kahnooj County, Tomgoran, 28°01'48.2" N, 57°44'22.2" E, 528 m, 15.v.2017–28.v.2017, Malaise trap (S.M. Madjdzadeh leg.).

Distribution in Iran: Fars, Kerman (present study).

Distribution outside Iran: Egypt, Saudi Arabia ([Gadallah & El-Barty, 2011](#)).

Parabatozonus fuliginosus* (Klug, 1834)*

Material examined: Iran, Kerman province: 1♂, Kahnooj County, Deh Kahan, 27°41'52.8" N, 57°32'10.7" E, 785 m, 23.v.2017–04.vii.2017, Malaise trap (S.M. Madjdzadeh leg.); 1♂, Mijan, Sarasiyab, 27°41'52.8" N, 57°32'10.7" E, 785 m, 05.v.2017–23.v.2017, Malaise trap, (S.M. Madjdzadeh leg.).

Distribution in Iran: Sistan-o Baluchestan, Kerman (present study).

Distribution outside Iran: Egypt, Central to South Africa, Saudi Arabia, Yemen ([Wahis, 2000](#); [Gadallah & El-Barty, 2011](#)).

Paracyphononyx ruficrus* (Klug, 1834)*

Material examined: Iran, Kerman province: 1♀, Kerman County, Rayen, 29°21'21.98" N, 57°21'15.88" E, 2678 m, 05.vii.2018, Swept on *Medicago sativa* L. (Sh. Mohebban leg.), 1♂, Kahnooj-Ghuch abad, 28°03'37.2" N, 57°48'32.1" E, 492 m, 21.iv.2017–08.v.2017, Malaise trap, (M. Purrezaali leg.).

Distribution in Iran: Fars, Sistan-o Baluchestan, Kerman (present study).

Distribution outside Iran: Asia Minor, Africa, Saudi Arabia, Yemen ([Wahis, 2002](#)), Egypt, South Africa, Zimbabwe ([Arnold, 1936](#)), Israel ([Haupt, 1962](#)).

Pseudopompilus humboldti* (Dahlbom, 1845)*

Material examined: Iran, Kerman province: 1♀, Jiroft County, Jiroft, 28°36'13.7" N, 57°49'42.0" E, 652 m, 23.v.2017–04.vi.2017, Malaise trap, (M. Purrezaali leg.).

Distribution in Iran: Isfahan, Kerman (present study).

Distribution outside Iran: Eastern Anatolia ([Yildirim & Wahis, 2010](#)).

Discussion

Prior to this study, only six pompilid species belonging to four genera and two subfamilies, Pompilinae and pepsinae, had been reported from Kerman province (Gussakovskij, 1932; Ebrahimi, 2006; Ebrahimi et al., 2008; Wolf et al., 2009). In the present study seventeen species were collected from Kerman province (South-Eastern Iran). Of them, four species, *Ceropales juncoi*, *Ceropales krieckbaumeri*, *Ceropales maroccana* (Ceropalinae) and *Agenioideus gentilis* (Pompilinae) were recorded for the first time for Iran, increasing the number of known Pompilidae species from 162 to 166 species. In the present research, all pompilid species are recorded for the first time from Kerman province increasing the number of pompilid species in Kerman from six to 23. Previous papers showed that many regions of the country have not been investigated well and the major part of pompilid species had been recorded in North (Mazandaran, Golestan), South-central (Fars) and Southeastern (Sistan-o Baluchestan) Iran (Enayatnia et al., 2018), so we assume that a large number of species remain to be discovered. It is necessary to emphasize that the current study could be considered as only a small part of investigations aiming at completing knowledge on faunal diversity of this diverse group of parasitoids in Iran. Further taxonomic investigations together with biological and behavioral data are necessary to increase the knowledge of diversity and applicability of this group of insects in Kerman province as well as other parts of Iran.

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Conflict of Interests

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest regarding the publication of this paper.

References

- Aguiar, A., Deans, A., Engel, M., Forshage, M., Huber, J., Jennings, J., Johnson, J., Arkady, S., Lelej, A., Longino, J., Lohrmann, V., Mikó, I., Ohl, M., Rasmussen, C., Taeger, A. & Yu, D. (2013) Order Hymenoptera. Animal Biodiversity: An Outline of Higherlevel Classification and Survey of Taxonomic Richness (Addenda 2013). *Zootaxa*, 3703 (1), 51-62.
<https://doi.org/10.11646/zootaxa.3703.1.12>
- Amiresmaili, N., Iranipour, S., Ebrahimi, E. & Barari, H. (2010a) Faunistic study of spider wasps (Hymenoptera: Pompilidae) from Mazandaran province (Iran). In: *Proceedings of 19th Iranian Plant Protection Congress, 2010, 31 July- 3 August, Tehran, Iran*. Iranian Research Institute of Plant Protection, Tehran, pp. 126.
- Amiresmaili, N., Iranipour, S., Ebrahimi, E., Barari, H. & Wahis, R. (2010b) Spider wasps (Hymenoptera, Pompilidae) from north of Iran, Mazandaran. *Entomofauna*, 31(9), 85-96.
- Amiresmaili, N., Wahis, R. & Barari, H. (2011) Contribution to the knowledge of the spider wasps fauna (Hymenoptera, Pompilidae) from Mazandaran province, Iran. *Entomofauna*, 29, 397-412.
- Amiresmaili, N. & Barari, H. (2012) Structure of dominance in the population of spider wasps (Hymenoptera: Pompilidae) in Mazandaran province of Iran. In: *Proceedings of 20th Iranian Plant Protection Congress, 2012, 26-29 August, Shiraz, Iran*. University of Shiraz, Shiraz, pp. 191.

- Arnold, G. (1936) The Psammocharidae (olim Pompilidae) of the Ethiopian region. Part 6. Subfamily Psammocharinae continued. *Annals of the Transvaal Museum*, 18, 415–460.
- Baghirov, R. T-o. (2014) New data on the spider wasps (Hymenoptera, Pompilidae) from the Western Siberia. *Fars Eastern Entomologist*, 279, 1–10.
- Ebrahimi, E. (2006) First report of 34 wasps of family Pompilidae from Iran. *Newsletter of Entomological Society of Iran*, 33, 1 (in Persian).
- Ebrahimi, E., Schmid-Egger, C. & Wahis, R. (2008) New records of Pompilidae (Hymenoptera) from Iran. *Linzer Biologische Beiträge*, 40 (2), 1435–1442.
- Enayatnia, M., Rakhshani, E., Kroupa, A. & Schmid-Egger, C. (2018) Updated catalogue of Pompilidae (Hymenoptera) in Iran. *Zootaxa*, 4394(4), 451–489.
<https://dx.doi.org/10.11646/zootaxa.4394.4.1>
- Falahatpishe, A., Fallahzadeh, M. & Wahis, R. (2016) A preliminary study of the spider wasp fauna (Hymenoptera, Pompilidae) from Southern Iran. *Entomologie Faunistique – Faunistic Entomology*, 69, 29–36.
- Gadallah, N.S. & El-Barty, A.F. (2011) Spider wasps collected from the western region of Saudi Arabia (Hymenoptera: Pompilidae). *Zoology in the Middle East*, 53, 99–106.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/09397140.2011.10648867>
- Gess, S.K. & Roosenchoon, P.A. (2016) A preliminary survey of flower visiting by aculeate wasps and bees in the Dubai Desert Conservation Reserve, UAE. *Journal of Hymenoptera Research*, 52, 81–141.
<https://doi.org/10.3897/jhr.52.10034>
- Grimaldi, D. & Engel, M.S. (2004) *Evolution of the Insects*. Cambridge University Press. 418 pp.
- Gussakovskij, V. (1932) Sphecidae i Psammocharidae (Hymenoptera), a cl. N. Zarudnyi in Persia orientali collectae (w/2 tab.). *Trudy Zoologicheskogo Instituta Akademii Nauk SSSR*, 1, 269–304.
- Haupt, H. (1962) The Pompilidae of Israel. *Bulletin of the Research Council of Israel, Jerusalem*, 11B, 1–70.
- Lelej, A.S. & Loktionov, V.M. (2012) 59. Fam. Pompilidae (*Psammocharidae*) – Spider wasps. In: Lelej A.S. (Ed.). *Annotated catalogue of the insects of Russian Far East. Volume I. Hymenoptera*. Vladivostok: Dalnauka, pp. 407–414 (in Russian).
- Móczár, L. (1968) Ergebnisse der zoologischen Forschungen von Dr. Z. Kaszab in der Mongolei. 167. Pompilidae (Hymenoptera). *Acta Zoologica Academiae Scientiarum Hungaricae*, 14 (3/4), 427–439.
- Móczár, L. (1986) Revision of the genus *Hemiceropaes* Priesner, 1969 (Hymenoptera: Ceropalidae). *Acta Zoologica Hungarica*, 32(3-4), 317–342.
- Móczár, L. (1989) Revision of the *helvetica*-group of the genus *Ceropaes* Latreille (Hym., Ceropalidae). *Beiträge zur Entomologie*, 39, 1 S, 9–61.
- Özbek, H.E., Yildirim, E., Wolf, H. & Wahis, R. (1999) The Pompilidae (Hymenoptera, Aculeata) fauna of Turkey. Part1: Ceropalinae and Pepsinae. *Zoology in the Middle East*, 18, 91–105.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/09397140.1999.10637785>
- Pitts, J.P., Wasbauer, M.S. & Von Dohlen, C.D. (2006) Preliminary morphological analysis of relationships between the spider wasp subfamilies (Hymenoptera: Pompilidae): revisiting an old problem. *Zoologica Scripta*, 35 (1), 63–84. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1463-6409.2005.00217.x>
- Priesner, H. (1965) Zur Kenntnis der Pompiliden Griechenlands. *Aus den Sitzungsberichten der Österreichischen Akademie der Wissenschaften*, 174, 55–78.
https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-662-24642-9_1
- Schmid-Egger, C. (2017) Order Hymenoptera, family Pompilidae. *Arthropod fauna of the UAE*, 6, 350–416.
- Schmid-Egger, C., Enayatnia, M., & Rakhshani, E. (2018) Review of the genus *Microcurgus* Haupt, 1950 (Hymenoptera, Pompilidae) with description of a new species from Iran. *Zootaxa*, 4444 (5), 530–536.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.11646/zootaxa.4444.5.2>
- van Achterberg, C. (2009) Can Townes type Malaise traps be improved some recent developments. *Entomologische Berichten*, 69 (4), 129–135.

- van Noort, S. (2019) *WaspWeb: Hymenoptera of the Afrotropical region*. Available from: <http://www.waspweb.org/> [Accessed on 24th November 2019].
- Wahis, R. (1963) Hyménoptères Pompilides de Yougoslavie (Hymenoptera: Pompilidae). *Fragmenta Balcanica* 4, 165–191.
- Wahis, R. (1979) Sur quelques Pompilides rares de la faune belge (Hymenoptera: Pompilidae). *Bulletin des Recherches Agronomiques de Gembloux* 14, 187–194.
- Wahis, R. (1996) Cadastre of biodiversity of Kyrghysistan. *Bishkek*, 3, 376–378.
- Wahis, R. (2000) Hyménoptères aculéates du Yemen (Pompilidae, Vespidae). *Notes Fauniques de Gembloux*, 41, 73–100.
- Wahis, R. (2002) *Ctenagenia ozbeki* sp. n., Pompilide nouveau de Turquie et d'Asie mineure (Hymenoptera: Pompilidae, Pompilinae). *Notes Fauniques de Gembloux*, 49, 115–123.
- Wahis, R. (2015) *Fauna Europaea: Pompilidae*. Fauna Europaea version 2.4. Available from <http://www.faunaeur.org/> (Accessed 22th October 2019).
- Wahis, R. & Schmid-Egger, C. (2002) The genus *Eoferreola* Arnold, 1935 in the Palaearctis with description of a new species (Hymenoptera: Pompilidae). *Notes Fauniques de Gembloux*, 46, 39–73.
- Waichert, C., Rodriguez, J., Wasbauer, M.S., Dohlen, C.D. & Pitts, J.P. (2015) Molecular phylogeny and systematics of spider wasps (Hymenoptera: Pompilidae): redefining subfamily boundaries and the origin of the family. *Zoological Journal of the Linnean Society*, 175 (2), 271–287. <https://doi.org/10.1111/zoj.12272>
- Wasbauer, M.S. (1995) Pompilidae. In: Hanson, P.E. & Gauld, I.D. (eds.) *The Hymenoptera of Costa Rica*. Oxford University Press, Oxford, pp. 522–539.
- Wolf, H. (1971) Prodromus der Hymenopteren der Tschechoslowakei. *Acta Fauna Entomologica Musei Nationalis Pragae*, 14 (Supplement 3), 1–176.
- Wolf, H. (1985) Zur Kenntnis der Gattung *Agenioideus* Ashmead, 1902 (Hymenoptera, Pompilidae). *Linzer Biologische Beiträge*, 17 (1), 223–258.
- Wolf, H. (1986) Zur Kenntnis der Gattung *Agenioideus* Ashmead, 1902 (Hymenoptera, Pompilidae) II. *Linzer Biologische Beiträge*, 18 (1), 5–84.
- Wolf, H. (1988) Über einige von Gussakovskij, F. Morawitz und Radoszkovski beschriebene sowie Bemerkungen zu einigen anderen Wegwespen-Arten (Hym. Pom.). *Linzer Biologische Beiträge*, 20 (1), 217–252.
- Wolf, H. (1990) Zur Kenntnis der Gattung *Agenioideus* Ashmead, 1902 (Hymenoptera, Pompilidae). III. *Linzer Biologische Beiträge*, 22 (2), 517–559.
- Wolf, H. (1995) Über bekannte und unbekannte Wegwespen (Hymenoptera, Pompilidae) aus Turkmenistan. *Linzer biologische Beiträge*, 27, 887–900.
- Wolf, H. (1998a) Wegwespen (Hymenoptera, Pompilidae) des Oberösterreichischen Landesmuseums Linz (Austria) aus Zentralasien. *Linzer biologische Beiträge*, 30 (1), 331–348.
- Wolf, H. (1998b) Wegwespen (Hymenoptera, Pompilidae) des Oberösterreichischen Landesmuseums Linz (Austria) aus Jordanien und Syrien. II. *Linzer biologische Beiträge*, 30 (1), 321–329.
- Wolf, H. (2003) Wegwespen aus Zentralasien und dem Iran (Hymenoptera, Pompilidae). *Linzer biologische Beiträge*, 35, 801–811.
- Wolf, H. (2004) Wegwespen (Hymenoptera, Pompilidae) des Oberösterreichischen Landesmuseums Linz (Austria) aus Syrien und Tunesien. *Linzer biologische Beiträge*, 36 (2), 1153–1173.
- Wolf, H. (2005a) Wegwespen (Hymenoptera, Pompilidae) des Oberösterreichischen Landesmuseums Linz (Austria) aus Zentralasien (II) und Mongolei. *Linzer biologische Beiträge*, 37 (2), 1737–1763.
- Wolf, H. (2005b) Wegwespen (Hymenoptera, Pompilidae) des Ober-österreichischen Landesmuseums Linz (Austria) aus Jordanien, Syrien, Tunesien und Oman. *Linzer biologische Beiträge*, 37 (2), 1765–1784.

- Wolf, H., Sorg, M., Stenmans, W. & Schwan, H. (2009) Wegwespen (Hymenoptera, Pompilidae) der westlichen Paläarktis bearbeitet von Heinrich Wolf 1948-2008. *Mitteilungen aus dem Entomologischen Verein Krefeld*, 3, 395 pp.
- Yasumatsu, K. (1946) Hymenoptera aculeate collected by Mr. K. Tsuneki in North China and inner Mongolia. II. Vespoidea 1. *Mushi*, 17, 13-18.
- Yasumatsu, K. & Ishikawa, R. (1955) Four new or little known Pompilidae from Japan (Hymenoptera). *Mushi*, 29 (7), 47-50.
- Yildirim, E. & Wahis, R. (2010) The distribution and biogeography of Pompilidae (Hymenoptera: Aculeata) in Turkey. *Faunistic Entomology*, 63, 23-34.
- Yildirim E. & Wahis R. (2011a) The distribution and biogeography of Pompilidae in Turkey (Hymenoptera: Aculeata). *Faunistic Entomology*, 63(1), 23-34.
- Yildirim, E. & Wahis, R. (2011b) Contribution to the knowledge of the Pompilidae (Hymenoptera, Aculeata) fauna of Turkey with the checklist of species. *Turkish Journal of Zoology*, 35 (5), 677- 688.
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زنبورهای عنكبوت خوار (Hymenoptera: Pompilidae) در جنوب شرقی ایران، کرمان

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چکیده: فون زنبورهای عنكبوت خوار (Hymenoptera: Pompilidae) استان کرمان (جنوب شرقی ایران) بررسی شد. در مجموع ۱۷ گونه متعلق به ۱۲ جنس از سه زیرخانواده Ceropalinae, Pepsinae و Pompilinae در طی سال‌های ۱۳۹۶ تا ۱۳۹۸ جمع‌آوری و شناسایی شدند. از بین گونه‌های جمع‌آوری شده، سه گونه از زیرخانواده Ceropalinae شامل *Ceropales juncoi* Giner, 1945، *Ceropales kriechbaumeri* Magretti, 1884 و *Ceropales maroccana* de Beaumont, 1947 یک گونه از زیرخانواده Pompilinae به نام *Agenioideus gentilis* (Klug, 1834) برای اولین بار از ایران گزارش می‌شوند. پراکنش جغرافیایی گونه‌ها ارایه شده است.

واژگان کلیدی: بال‌غشاییان، زنبورهای عنكبوت خوار، فون، گزارش‌های جدید، ایران